

Thermodynamic Analysis of Continuous Vibrating Fluidised Bed Drying of Grain

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Abstract

The performance of continuous vibrating fluidised bed drying of corn grits was simulated (using a previously validated mathematical model) and analysed based on the first- and second law of thermodynamics. The energy and exergy analyses were performed for several drying conditions. The effects of inlet air velocity and temperature, vibration intensity, and particle size on the efficiencies and inefficiencies of drying process have been simulated and discussed. Generally, application of vibration during fluidised bed drying enhanced the drying process. The application of higher levels of drying air temperature and velocity led in higher exergy efficiencies and energy utilisation. Also, the exergy loss had maximum value when higher drying air temperature and velocity were used for the drying process.

1. Introduction

Commercial application of vibrating fluidised bed dryers has been increasing over the past decade for economic drying of wide size particles and difficult-to-fluidise sticky powders. The principle of the vibrating fluidised bed can be used as a strategy to improve the quality of fluidisation of irregular and cohesive materials and to avoid problems like channelling, defluidisation and slug flow as well as to improve the drying kinetics.

Drying is a process that requires high energy input because of latent heat of water vaporisation and relatively low energy efficiency of industrial dryers, thus making it one of the most energy-intensive operations with great significance. For instance, drying accounts for 10 % of all energy consumption in the food industry [1]. Nowadays, one of the most important challenges of the industrial drying is to reduce the cost of energy sources for good quality dried products. In this regard, it is essential to perform an effective thermal analysis of continuous drying processes to provide energy savings and optimum processing conditions. As known, exergy analysis evaluates the availability energy at different points in a system. Exergy analysis leads to a better understanding of the influence of thermodynamic phenomena on the process efficiency, comparison of the importance of

different thermodynamic factors and the determination of the most efficient ways of improving the process under consideration [2].

In recent years, several studies have been conducted on energy and exergy analyses of food drying [3,4]. The literature review showed that very little information is available on the effect of drying condition on energy and exergy analysis of continuous vibrating fluidised bed drying of moist materials such as grain, vegetables and fruits. Building on the results of an earlier study [5], the present work was aimed to analyse the energy and exergy performance of continuous vibrating fluidised bed drying process of corn grits at various operating conditions.

2. Theoretical Principle

By means of schematic representation, the main feature of a continuous plug-flow vibrating fluidised bed drying chamber, input and output terms of solid and gas, and the heat loss to surrounding is depicted in Figure 1 [2].

Figure 1: Schematic of drying process with input and output terms.

2.1 Energy analysis

The energy utilisation (Eu) is calculated by applying the first law of thermodynamics as follows:

$$Eu = m_g (h_1 - h_3) \quad (1)$$

where m is the mass flow rate and h is the enthalpy. The subscript g denotes gas. The mass flow rate of the gas (m_g) is calculated using the following equation:

$$m_g = \rho_g v_g A_d \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the density, v is the velocity and A_d is the drying area. The enthalpy of the drying gas can be determined as follows:

$$h = c_{p_g} (T - T_{ref}) + \lambda Y \quad (3)$$

where T is the temperature, Y is the gas humidity, λ is the latent heat of vaporisation and c_p is the specific heat. The subscript *ref* denotes reference value. The energy utilisation ratio of drying chamber (*EUR*) is calculated using the following equation:

$$EUR = \frac{(h_1 - h_3)}{(h_1 - h_e)} \quad (4)$$

2.2 Exergy analysis

The total exergy of inflow, outflow and losses was determined in the scope of the second law analysis of thermodynamics. The basic procedure for exergy analysis of drying chamber was to calculate the exergy flow values at steady-state points and determine the reason of exergy variation for the process.

The exergy flow values were calculated using the characteristics of the working medium from the first law energy balance. For this purpose, the general form of applicable exergy equation was employed for steady flow systems.

$$\dot{Ex} = m_g c_{p_g} \left[(T - T_{ref}) - T_{ref} \ln \left(\frac{T}{T_{ref}} \right) \right] \quad (5)$$

The exergy efficiency provides a true measure of the performance of the drying system from the thermodynamic viewpoint. In defining the exergy efficiency, it is necessary to identify both the exergy loss and the exergy input. In this study, the exergy loss is the rate of exergy evaporation for drying the products and the exergy input is the rate of exergy drying gas entering the dryer chamber. The exergy loss in the drying chamber can be determined as follows:

$$\dot{Ex}_l = \dot{Ex}_1 - \dot{Ex}_3 \quad (6)$$

The exergy efficiency can be defined as the ratio of exergy use (investment) in the drying of the product to exergy of the drying gas supplied to the system [3]:

$$\dot{Ex}_{eff} = \frac{\dot{Ex}_1 - \dot{Ex}_l}{\dot{Ex}_1} = \frac{\dot{Ex}_3}{\dot{Ex}_1} \quad (7)$$

In this study, the dead state was considered to be the condition of the ambient at which the temperature, pressure and humidity were 25 °C, 101.325 kPa and 0.0024 kg water/kg dry air.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Model validation

Our previous presented model [5] for performance analysis of a continuous vibrating fluidised bed dryer was verified by using the experimental data reported elsewhere [6]. In order to examine the capability of the model, the calculated values of different parameters were compared with the corresponding experimental ones. The model results showed a fairly good agreement with said experimental data.

Figure 2: Comparison between experimental and calculated moisture content and solids temperature.

3.2 Energy analysis

The energy analysis for vibrating fluidised bed drying of corn grits was performed using the data obtained from simulation results. The basic data used in the simulations that follow were the same as those in Fig. 2. In all cases, a $\pm 15\%$ variation in the operating parameters was applied. The energy utilisation and energy utilisation ratio curves are shown in Figs. 3 and 4 for vibrating fluidised bed drying of corn grits at various operating conditions.

As can be seen from Fig. 3, energy utilisation and energy utilisation ratio initially decreased with the distance along the bed. The energy utilisation and energy utilisation ratio were high at the beginning of the process due to the rapid moisture loss of corn grits. After that, the energy utilisation and energy utilisation ratio presented a slight increase because the convection heat is not used to evaporate water; it is used to increase the solids temperature. Further, the energy utilisation and energy utilisation ratio increased with increase in drying air temperature due to the fact that high drying air temperatures cause a greater reduction of moisture content, in other words, at high temperatures the transfer of heat and mass is high and water loss is excessive. Similar findings have been reported in the literature [4].

Figure 3: Effect of drying air temperature on energy utilisation and energy utilisation ratio.

Figure 4 shows the effect of air velocity on the energy utilisation and energy utilisation ratio curves for vibrating fluidised bed drying of corn grits. It is observed that air velocity reduction of about 15% does not show any significant difference along the whole process. Thus, it would be advantageous to use a gas velocity as low as possible. However, there may be practical restriction due to the onset of fluidisation.

Figure 4: Effect of drying air velocity on energy utilisation and energy utilisation ratio.

Additionally, it was found that the vibration intensity and particle diameter had only a slight influence on the energy utilisation and energy utilisation ratio (results not shown). In the case of the vibration intensity, it is probably due to the correlation used to account for the vibration parameters. The correlations that include the effect of this parameter in the literature seem to be equipment specific [5].

3.3 Exergy analysis

The exergy loss and exergy efficiency curves are shown in Figs. 5 and 6 for continuous vibrating fluidized bed drying of corn grits as influenced by air temperature and air velocity, respectively. As can be seen from Figs. 5 and 6, the exergy loss initially increased and then decreased continually with the distance along the bed. This can be explained by the fact that the moisture content of corn grits decreased with the distance along the bed and

the capability of product to absorb and use the exergy for evaporation decreased continually, therefore, the exhaust air had more proportion of incoming exergy.

Figure 5: Effect of drying air temperature on exergy loss and exergy efficiency.

Increasing the drying air temperature increased exergy loss because of the higher drying temperatures possessed a large amount of entering exergy and great proportion of inflow exergy utilised for moisture evaporation. Increasing the air velocity increased exergy loss, especially at the early stages of the drying process. Then, the exergy loss is substantially similar for the range of velocities employed.

Figure 6: Effect of drying air velocity on exergy loss and exergy efficiency.

As can be seen from Figs. 5 and 6, the exergy efficiency increased continually with the distance along the bed. Increasing the drying temperature caused an increase in exergy loss but this was less than the increased amount of exergy entered. Therefore, the exergy efficiency increased with increasing in drying air temperature, according to Eq. (7). Increasing the air velocity caused also an increase in exergy efficiency, as shown in Fig. 6. At the early stages of the drying process, the exergy efficiency is substantially similar for the three velocities employed, but at the end of the drying process the exergy efficiency is higher at high velocities.

Additionally, it was found that the vibration intensity and particle diameter had only a slight influence on the exergy loss and exergy efficiency (results not shown).

It is worth noting that the most industrial dryers are scaled up based on experimental obtained from laboratory drying systems. The continuous vibrating fluidised bed drying process is usually scaled up based on thermodynamics, fluid dynamics, drying kinetics considerations, bed depth, superficial fluidisation velocity, and throughput, amongst others. Accordingly, the presented energetic and exergetic performance assessment could successfully applied to distinguish the proper drying conditions to achieve the optimal exergy efficiency in industrial continuous vibrating fluidised bed drying systems.

4. Conclusions

The energetic and exergetic performance of continuous vibrating fluidised bed drying of corn grits were simulated using a validated mathematical model. It was found that the variation of operating parameters influenced dryer performance. For instance, energy utilisation and energy utilisation ratio increased with increase in drying air temperature and velocity. Exergy loss increased with increase in drying air temperature and velocity. Exergy efficiency increased with increase in drying air temperature and velocity. It is more advantageous to apply lower levels of inlet air velocities by taking into account the minimum fluidisation velocity and fully fluidisation conditions. Additionally, it was found that the vibration intensity and particle diameter had only a slight influence on the energetic and exergetic dryer performance. Further work is needed to make the mathematical model a useful tool for energetic and exergetic analyses.

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